

Numerical assessment of the high cycle fatigue behavior of high strength steels affected by shear-cutting operations

L.A. Gonçalves Junior ^{a,b} ^{*},
L.G. Barbu ^{a,b} ^{*}

^a Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya - BarcelonaTech (UPC), Campus Norte UPC, 08034 Barcelona, Spain

^b Centre Internacional de Mètodes Numèrics en l'Enginyeria (CIMNE), Campus Norte UPC, 08034 Barcelona, Spain

^c Luleå University of Technology, Department of Engineering Sciences and Mathematics, Division of Solid Mechanics, Luleå, 971 87, Sweden

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Trimming
Punching
High cycle fatigue simulation
Fatigue life estimation
Finite element method

ABSTRACT

Shear-cutting processes are arguably among the most preferred technologies for performing material removal operations in the manufacturing of chassis components due to the combination of high production rate and cost-efficiency. Nevertheless, they may severely jeopardize the fatigue response of high strength metals, compromising the current trend of using this class of materials for weight reduction of automotive chassis parts. Thus, the generation of reliable data featuring the influence of these operations on the material fatigue behavior is essential to further support this lightweighting tendency. Commonly employed for this aim, traditional fatigue tests are usually time-consuming and rather expensive. In this context, numerical simulations arise as a viable alternative, providing not only material-related information but also assisting engineers in the design of new components. In this work, an isotropic damage-based high cycle fatigue model is employed to estimate the fatigue life of trimmed and punched specimens of two complex phase steels. The residual stresses obtained from each process simulation and the roughness measured on the cut surface are included in the model to account for the influence of these operations on the material fatigue strength. Furthermore, standard uniaxial tensile properties and S–N data resulting from fatigue tests on as-polished specimens are the only material information required. A good agreement is found between the numerical fatigue life predictions and the experimental measurements, remaining below an error factor of three for all the estimated cases. In addition to coupon specimens, the model is also readily extensible to component-level applications, enabling the fatigue assessment of metallic engineering structures featuring shear-cut surfaces.

1. Introduction

The contemporary automotive industry is continuously seeking weight reduction opportunities to increase market competitiveness and mitigate its environmental impact. In particular, this segment has been massively pushed in recent years toward the conception of lightweight solutions to support the development of highly efficient vehicles that meet the requirements of the upcoming net-zero energy paradigm. Traditionally, body-in-white (BiW) and chassis have been mainly focused as areas with major potential for the implementation of these solutions, since they represent, respectively, around 40% and 25% of the vehicle total weight [1]. From a material perspective, advanced high strength steels (AHSS) have become dominant in the design of BiW parts due to the good in-service performance, manufacturability and recyclability provided by them at affordable costs [2–4]. Furthermore, they have been also employed for the production of chassis components [5]. In

these cases, however, a special attention should be destined to the fatigue behavior of the selected material, as these parts are usually subjected to cyclic loads in the in-service condition.

AHSS are remarkably characterized by high ultimate strength levels, commonly varying from 600 to 1500 MPa. However, particularly high strengths achieved by the steels of this class (higher than 800 MPa) are usually associated with a substantial increase in their notch sensitivity and, ultimately, with limitations in their crack resistance and formability [2,6]. This characteristic poses a major challenge to the use of these materials in lightweight automotive parts, typically obtained from steel sheets through manufacturing operations, such as forming and shear cutting, that intrinsically introduce surface irregularities and edge defects to the final component [7,8]. The presence of these defects is notably harmful for the material fatigue resistance, since they act as preferential sites for crack nucleation and propagation under subcritical

^{*} Corresponding authors.

E-mail addresses: lagoncalves@cimne.upc.edu (L.A. Gonçalves Junior), erik.1.olsson@ltu.se (E. Olsson), lgratiela@cimne.upc.edu (L.G. Barbu).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfatigue.2025.109178>

Received 10 April 2025; Received in revised form 29 June 2025; Accepted 17 July 2025

Available online 5 August 2025

0142-1123/© 2025 The Authors. Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Nomenclature

$\alpha_r (R)$	Coefficient of the HCF constitutive model
$\sigma, \sigma_0, \sigma_i$	Stress, effective stress and inelastic stress
$\sigma_{res,mi}, \sigma_{res}$	Initial and relaxed residual stress tensors
ϵ	Strain tensor
$\dot{\mu}, d$	Damage consistency factor and damage internal variable
η, tol	Relative error and convergence tolerance of the advance in time strategy algorithm
$\mathbb{C}_0, \mathbb{C}^s, \mathbb{C}^t$	Elastic constitutive, secant constitutive and tangent constitutive tensors
$\mathcal{K}, \mathcal{K}_0$	Damage and effective damage thresholds
$\bar{\mathbb{F}}(f(\sigma_0), \mathcal{K}_0, f_{red}(\gamma))$	Threshold damage function
$\psi, \dot{\epsilon}, \kappa_p$	Free energy per unit mass, dissipation potential and normalized plastic energy dissipation
σ^0, ϵ^0	Uniaxial stress at the proportional limit and the corresponding uniaxial strain
σ_a, R	Stress amplitude and stress ratio
σ_n, τ	Normal and shear stress components at the critical plane for fracture
$\sigma_{max}, \sigma_{min}$	Estimated actual maximum and minimum equivalent stresses
$\sigma'_{max}, \sigma_{avg}$	Calculated maximum equivalent and cross-sectional average stresses
$a_r, S_{u,min}$	Material and process-related parameters
$f(\sigma_0), f_{HCF}(\sigma_0, f_{red}(\gamma))$	Stress norm function and stress norm function modified by fatigue state function
$f_{red}(\gamma)$	Fatigue state function
f_{rel}, f_d	Stress relaxation and critical plane directional factors
$G(\cdot), G_{HCF}(f(\sigma_0), f_{red}(\gamma))$	Monotonically increasing scalar function and monotonically increasing scalar function modified by the fatigue state function
G_f, g_{f_0}, g_f	Fracture energy, initial volumetric fracture energy and updated volumetric fracture energy
h_t	Logarithm exponent used in the estimation of the actual maximum stress
J_2	Second invariant of the deviatoric stress
K_{res}, K_r, K_t	Residual stress, surface roughness and stress concentration factors
l_c	Characteristic length of the finite element
m^0, E, ν	Material density, Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio
n_{crit}	Unit vector normal to the critical plane for fracture
N_c, N_d, N_f	Number of cycles, number of cycles to the damage initiation point and number of cycles at the intersection between the fatigue state function and the normalized S–N–R surface affected by the shear-cutting operation
$r(\sigma_0)$	Principal stress weight factor
R_z	Mean peak to valley height of the cut surface roughness profile in μm

$S'(R, N_c), S(R, N_c)$	Fatigue strengths of the material in the as-polished condition and affected by the shear-cutting operation
$S'_{th}(R), S_{th}(R)$	Fatigue limit functions of the material in the as-polished condition and affected by the shear-cutting operation
S_e, S_u	Material fatigue limit at $R = -1$ and ultimate tensile strength
$S_{th,R1}, AUX R1, \alpha_f, \beta_f, S_{th,R2}, AUX R2$	Fatigue material parameters

cantly alter the material properties in the shear-affected zone (SAZ), especially the roughness of the cut surface, while also introducing residual stresses [9,10]. Accordingly, the comparison of these operations with other cutting technologies, e.g. milling and laser, reveals that they tend to generate a higher degradation of the material fatigue strength than the other manufacturing processes [11,12]. Yet, punching and trimming have been and are likely to remain the preferred technologies to perform material removal operations in the fabrication of sheet-like and chassis automotive parts due to the combination of high production rate and cost-efficiency provided by them [9].

Chassis parts are usually designed to withstand a high number of load cycles (over 10^5 cycles) throughout their lifetime. Thus, the availability of engineering data in the so-called high cycle fatigue (HCF) regime is crucial for the efficient design of such components. Commonly obtained by means of the standardized staircase method [13], the generation of experimental data characterizing the influence of shear-cutting operations in the fatigue behavior of AHSS grades is time-consuming, expensive and, hence, limited. For instance, a comprehensive characterization of these processes should consider the combination of different cutting strategies (e.g. one or multiple-stage operations) with several clearance values to generate a set of design-relevant stress amplitude-life (S–N) curves for each material [9,14,15]. Owing to this limitation, numerical schemes which account for the effects of these manufacturing operations in the fatigue simulations constitute important modeling tools to bridge the gap of information left by the experimental data, assisting engineers in the decision-making process of designing new components.

In this work, a HCF model is proposed to numerically reproduce the uniaxial fatigue tests on trimmed and punched specimens fabricated from two AHSS grades: the complex phases HR CP800SF and HR CP980SF. Employed as the general numerical framework, the nonlinear HCF constitutive formulation initially proposed by Oller et al. [16] is further developed to incorporate the effects of these processes in the fatigue modeling. Accordingly, the residual stresses resulting from the process simulations and the roughness measured on the cut surfaces are included in the model as factors affecting the fatigue strength of the base material. The entire load history until the specimen failure is simulated. For the sake of computational efficiency, the cycle-jump algorithm presented in [17] is used as advance in time strategy. The proposed model can not only handle simulations of coupon specimens, but is also extensible to component-level applications, enabling the assessment of metallic engineering structures whose fatigue strength is affected by shear-cutting operations.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, the HCF constitutive formulation is devised. Section 3 describes the modeling approach employed in the simulations of the trimming and punching processes and the process-related data included in the fatigue model. In Section 4, the calibration of the model material parameters is presented. In Section 5, the obtained numerical results are validated against the experimental observations. Finally, concluding remarks are provided in Section 6.

cyclic loads. In particular, the fatigue strength of AHSS is greatly affected by process parameters such as cutting clearance and shearing strategy of trimming and punching operations, because they signifi-

2. Constitutive formulation

The HCF constitutive formulation established by Oller et al. [16] is grounded in the principle that, from a phenomenological perspective, high cycle fatigue in metals is mainly driven by two dominant mechanisms: strength reduction due to the initiation and propagation of micro-cracks under sub-critical stresses (well below S_y) and stiffness loss resulting from the coalescence of micro- into macro-cracks, with a consequent reduction of resistant cross-sectional area. Conceived in the framework of the continuum damage mechanics (CDM), this constitutive formulation incorporates both effects by means of an isotropic damage model modified by a fatigue state function that accounts for the progressive deterioration of the material strength due to the application of cyclic loads. Following the descriptive format presented by Gonçalves Junior et al. [18], this model is extended in this work to include the effects of residual stresses and surface roughness affecting the material fatigue strength.

2.1. Thermodynamic principles and constitutive equation

Originally formulated for any thermomechanical process, the constitutive model proposed in [16] is here particularized for purely mechanical processes, i.e., with negligible thermal effects, under the regime of infinitesimal strains. Thus, the assumption of a free energy,

$$\psi(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}, d) = \frac{1}{2m^0} (1-d) \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} : \mathbb{C}_0 : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}, \quad (1)$$

defined as a function of the strain tensor, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$, and the damage internal variable, d , is taken as the starting point for its development. Here, d , is a scalar-valued variable that accounts for the deterioration of the material stiffness. It ranges from 0 when the material is in the intact condition to 1 when it is fully damaged. Moreover, the term m^0 refers to the material density and \mathbb{C}_0 denotes the constitutive tensor in the undamaged state. Analogously, all the variables represented with the subscript 0 in the following are related to the undamaged space (i.e., effective space), whereas the rest refer to the real one.

Following this, the second law of thermodynamics in the form of Clausius–Planck inequality,

$$\dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} = \underbrace{\left(\boldsymbol{\sigma} - m^0 \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} \right)}_{\text{constitutive relation}} : \dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} - \underbrace{m^0 \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial d}}_{\text{damage dissipation}} \cdot \dot{d} \geq 0, \quad (2)$$

is employed to account for the irreversible phenomena in the constitutive model.

Considering the restriction in which inequality (2) must hold for any mechanical process (i.e., $\forall \dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}$ admissible) and the derivatives of Eq. (1) with respect to $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$, one may readily obtain the Cauchy stress,

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = m^0 \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} = (1-d) \cdot \mathbb{C}_0 : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \underbrace{\mathbb{C}_0 : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_{\text{effective stress, } \boldsymbol{\sigma}_0} - d \cdot \underbrace{\mathbb{C}_0 : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_{\text{inelastic stress, } \boldsymbol{\sigma}_i}. \quad (3)$$

and the secant constitutive tensor,

$$\mathbb{C}^s = \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}}{\partial \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} = m^0 \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^2} = (1-d) \cdot \mathbb{C}_0, \quad (4)$$

that relates strain and stress when damage is not evolving, i.e., $\dot{d} = 0$.

In addition, the remaining part of inequality (3) leads to the energy dissipation rate which reads

$$m^0 \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial d} \cdot \dot{d} \geq 0. \quad (5)$$

Finally, to avoid the nucleation and propagation of cracks under compressive stress states, an additional constraint should be imposed to the material energy dissipation rate. Here, the weight factor,

$$r(\boldsymbol{\sigma}_0) = \frac{\sum_{I=1}^3 \langle \boldsymbol{\sigma}_I \rangle}{\sum_{I=1}^3 |\boldsymbol{\sigma}_I|}, \quad (6)$$

such that $r(\boldsymbol{\sigma}_0) < 0.5$ leads to $\dot{d} = 0$, is used for this purpose. Where $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_I$ represent the principal stresses and $\langle x \rangle = 0.5 [x + |x|]$ is the Macaulay's brackets.

2.2. Threshold damage function, evolution law and tangent constitutive tensor

To determine whether the material is in a linear or non-linear state the following convex, smooth and differentiable threshold damage function,

$$\begin{aligned} \overline{\mathbb{F}}(f(\boldsymbol{\sigma}_0), \mathcal{K}_0, f_{red}(\boldsymbol{\gamma})) &= \frac{G(f(\boldsymbol{\sigma}_0))}{f_{red}(\boldsymbol{\gamma})} - G(\mathcal{K}_0) \\ &= G_{HCF}(f(\boldsymbol{\sigma}_0), f_{red}(\boldsymbol{\gamma})) - G(\mathcal{K}_0) \leq 0, \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

is here introduced. Where $G(\cdot)$ is a suitable monotonically increasing scalar function, $f(\boldsymbol{\sigma}_0)$ a stress norm function, \mathcal{K}_0 the effective damage threshold, $f_{red}(\boldsymbol{\gamma})$ a fatigue state function defined in terms of a set of arguments, $\boldsymbol{\gamma}$, and $G_{HCF}(f(\boldsymbol{\sigma}_0), f_{red}(\boldsymbol{\gamma}))$ the ratio between $G(f(\boldsymbol{\sigma}_0))$ and $f_{red}(\boldsymbol{\gamma})$. Analogous to that, all the functions in the rest of this work denoted with the subscript *HCF* are modified by the fatigue state function, $f_{red}(\boldsymbol{\gamma})$. This state function irreversibly ranges from 1 to nearly 0 and acts, at last instance, amplifying the stress norm, $f(\boldsymbol{\sigma}_0)$, as a result of the application of cyclic loads. In its general form, it is defined in terms of the number of cycles N_c , the stress ratio, $R = \frac{\sigma_{min}}{\sigma_{max}}$, and maximum equivalent stress, σ_{max} , on each load cycle, such that $\boldsymbol{\gamma} = \{N_c, R, \sigma_{max}\}$. The definition of the stress norm, $f(\boldsymbol{\sigma}_0)$, in turn, depends on behavior of the material to be modeled. This work is focused on the simulation of AHSS which are pressure-insensitive materials. For this reason, the von Mises equivalent stress,

$$f(\boldsymbol{\sigma}_0) = \sqrt{3J_2}, \quad (8)$$

is chosen here as the stress norm function, with J_2 referring to the second invariant of the deviatoric stress tensor.

To fully characterize a dissipative constitutive model, the laws that govern the evolution of its internal variables need to be defined. Following here the format proposed by Simo and Ju [19], the evolution law of the internal variable d reads

$$\dot{d} = \dot{\mu} \cdot \frac{\partial \overline{\mathbb{F}}(f(\boldsymbol{\sigma}_0), \mathcal{K}_0, f_{red}(\boldsymbol{\gamma}))}{\partial f(\boldsymbol{\sigma}_0)} = \dot{\mu} \cdot \frac{\partial G_{HCF}(f(\boldsymbol{\sigma}_0), f_{red}(\boldsymbol{\gamma}))}{\partial f(\boldsymbol{\sigma}_0)}; \quad (9)$$

$$\dot{\mathcal{K}}_0 = \dot{\mu},$$

where $\dot{\mu}$ is a non-negative scalar-valued parameter called damage consistency factor which allows the definition of loading/unloading conditions according to the Kuhn–Tucker relations,

$$\dot{\mu} \geq 0; \quad \overline{\mathbb{F}}(f(\boldsymbol{\sigma}_0), \mathcal{K}_0, f_{red}(\boldsymbol{\gamma})) \leq 0; \quad \dot{\mu} \cdot \overline{\mathbb{F}}(f(\boldsymbol{\sigma}_0), \mathcal{K}_0, f_{red}(\boldsymbol{\gamma})) = 0. \quad (10)$$

From the combination of the threshold damage function (7), the evolution law (9) and the Kuhn–Tucker relations (10), one may easily obtain this consistency factor which is given by

$$\dot{\mu} = \dot{f}_{HCF}(\boldsymbol{\sigma}_0, f_{red}(\boldsymbol{\gamma})) = \dot{\mathcal{K}}_0. \quad (11)$$

The interpretation of Eq. (11) evidences that the damage effective threshold, \mathcal{K}_0 , acts as a historical variable that stores the maximum modified stress norm, $f_{HCF}(\boldsymbol{\sigma}_0, f_{red}(\boldsymbol{\gamma}))$, at a given material point, i.e.,

$$\mathcal{K}_0|_t = \max \left\{ \mathcal{K}_0^0, \max \left\{ f_{HCF}(\boldsymbol{\sigma}_0, f_{red}(\boldsymbol{\gamma})) \Big|_s \right\} \right\} \quad 0 \leq s \leq t, \quad (12)$$

where \mathcal{K}_0^0 defines the initial damage threshold.

In the same line, the damage internal variable d may be obtained through the time integration of Eq. (9)₁ combined with Eq. (11) as follows

$$d|_t = \int_t \dot{G}_{HCF}(f(\boldsymbol{\sigma}_0), f_{red}(\boldsymbol{\gamma})) dt. \quad (13)$$

Eq. (13) may be explicitly integrated by choosing a suitable monotonically increasing $G_{HCF}(f(\boldsymbol{\sigma}_0), f_{red}(\boldsymbol{\gamma}))$ function. Following the

Fig. 1. Uniaxial stress-strain curve for damage. From [21], used under Creative Commons CC-BY-NC-ND license.

choice presented in Gonçalves Junior et al. [18], d is expressed here as

$$d_{II}^j = d^{i-1} \cdot \frac{\mathcal{K}_0^{i-1}}{f_{HCF}^j(\sigma_0, f_{red}(\gamma))} \cdot \frac{\mathcal{K}_0^i - f_{HCF}^j(\sigma_0, f_{red}(\gamma))}{\mathcal{K}_0^i - \mathcal{K}_0^{i-1}} + d^i \cdot \frac{\mathcal{K}_0^i}{f_{HCF}^j(\sigma_0, f_{red}(\gamma))} \cdot \frac{f_{HCF}^j(\sigma_0, f_{red}(\gamma)) - \mathcal{K}_0^{i-1}}{\mathcal{K}_0^i - \mathcal{K}_0^{i-1}}, \quad (14)$$

for the Region II of the hardening-exponential softening material response shown in Fig. 1. Defined in term of linear piecewise segments, d_{II}^j in this region, such that $d^{i-1} \leq d_{II}^j \leq d^i$, represents the damage corresponding to the modified stress norm $f_{HCF}^j(\sigma_0, f_{red}(\gamma))$, with $i = 1 : n$ being the reference points at which the damages d^{i-1} and the effective thresholds \mathcal{K}_0^{i-1} are computed.

For the Region III, in turn, d is governed by the exponentially decaying function

$$d_{III} = 1 - \frac{\mathcal{K}^n}{f_{HCF}(\sigma_0, f_{red}(\gamma))} \cdot \exp \left\{ \frac{\frac{\mathcal{K}^n}{E} \cdot [f_{HCF}(\sigma_0, f_{red}(\gamma)) - \mathcal{K}_0^n]}{\frac{\mathcal{K}^n \mathcal{K}_0^n}{2E} - g_{f_{III}}} \right\}, \quad (15)$$

where \mathcal{K}^n and \mathcal{K}_0^n are the damage thresholds in the real and effective spaces at the n th point, E the material Young's modulus and $g_{f_{III}}$ the volumetric fracture energy corresponding to this region, computed as follows

$$g_{f_{III}} = g_f - \left\{ \frac{1}{2} \frac{(\sigma^0)^2}{E} + \sum_{i=2}^n \left[\frac{(\mathcal{K}^i + \mathcal{K}^{i-1}) \cdot (\mathcal{K}_0^i - \mathcal{K}_0^{i-1})}{2E} \right] - \frac{\mathcal{K}^n \mathcal{K}_0^n}{2E} \right\}. \quad (16)$$

In Eq. (16), σ^0 is the uniaxial stress at the material proportional limit which defines the initial damage threshold, \mathcal{K}_0^0 . In addition, g_{f_0} represents the total volumetric fracture energy resulting from the ratio of the material fracture energy, G_f , by the characteristic length, l_c . This ensures the consistency between regularized and non-regularized models in terms of the amount of energy dissipated in the crack [20].

Finally, the tangent operator, \mathbb{C}^t , in the rate constitutive equation,

$$\dot{\sigma} = \mathbb{C}^t : \dot{\varepsilon}, \quad (17)$$

relates stress and strain rates under damage evolution, i.e., $\dot{d} > 0$. It is given here by

$$\mathbb{C}^t = \mathbb{C}^s - \frac{\partial G_{HCF}(f(\sigma_0), f_{red}(\gamma))}{\partial f(\sigma_0)} \cdot (\mathbb{C}_0 : \varepsilon) \otimes \frac{\partial f(\mathbb{C}_0 : \varepsilon)}{\partial \varepsilon}, \quad (18)$$

with \mathbb{C}^s being the secant constitutive tensor of Eq. (4).

2.3. Residual stress relaxation effect

Residual stresses in solids are self-equilibrating stresses that typically arise as a result of inhomogeneous plastic flow or phase transformation induced by numerous manufacturing processes (e.g., machining, forming, shear and laser cutting, etc.) and material processing techniques such as quenching, casting, among others [22–24]. Although in equilibrium over the entire body, they are often sensitive to the application of monotonic, cyclic and thermal loading [25], tending to relax under these circumstances. The relaxation process under cyclic loads is a particularly complex phenomenon in which the underlying mechanisms are not fully understood yet. Even so, some remarkable conclusions may be drawn from existing works in the literature.

According to Hayama et al. [26], residual stresses exhibit an effect comparable to that of mean stress on the material fatigue limit. This means that, in general lines, the material fatigue performance is enhanced by the introduction of compressive residual stresses, usually accomplished through surface treatments such as shot peening, induction hardening, carburizing, to name a few. However, the stability of these stresses may be affected by a relaxation that is particularly remarkable when they, combined with compressive stresses generated by the applied load, are sufficiently high to exceed the material yield stress, as concluded by them [26] for three different high strength steels. In the same line, Han et al. [27] reported in a study conducted with steel welded specimens that the relaxation process is closely related with the material yield stress. As many other authors [28–31], they claim that a large stress relaxation (even more than 50%) usually takes place in the fatigue early stages due to a monotonic-like stress redistribution mechanism induced by the applied load. This phase is then followed by a lower-rate relaxation regime which is dependent on the number of cycles.

Several empirical [27,32–34] and physical-based [28] models have been proposed to account for the effect of residual stress relaxation under cyclic load. However, only a few of them can capture the initial relaxation. Following a format analogous to that proposed by Han et al. [27], the factor

$$f_{rel} = A \left[\frac{f(\sigma_{res_{ini}} + \sigma_0)}{\mathcal{K}_0^0} \right] + B, \quad \text{if } \max \left\{ f(\sigma_{res_{ini}} + \sigma_0) \right\} \Big|_{N_c} - \mathcal{K} > 0 \quad (19)$$

is here introduced to account for the monotonic-like stress relaxation. It is a scalar-valued irreversible factor initially equal to 1 that is

Fig. 2. Linear fitting to determine the constants A and B of the relaxation factor given by Eq. (19). Experimental data for 10% and 25% cutting clearances and the HT780 hot-rolled high-strength steel.

recomputed once at a given material point if – within a cycle, N_c , – the maximum norm of the initial residual stress, $\sigma_{res_{ini}}$, combined with the one induced by the applied load, σ_0 , exceeds the damage threshold in the real space, \mathcal{K} .

Contrarily to the predefined values (–1.6 and 2.6) set by Han et al. [27], the constants A and B are adopted in Eq. (19) to provide this stress relaxation model with more flexibility for a phenomenological fitting according to the experimental data available in the literature for high strength steels. The experimental investigation conducted by Shiozaki et al. [14] on the fatigue behavior of punched specimens is used here as a reference to calibrate the constants A and B . In this study, specimens made of two hot-rolled steels (HT540 and HT780) with 10% and 25% cutting clearances were tested. For both cases, the authors found an in-common linear relation between the initial residual stress and stabilized one measured at the end of the tests. The calibration is performed here using the HT780 steel because it exhibits mechanical properties that are closer to the materials investigated in the present work (i.e., 728 MPa and 796 MPa of measured yield stress and ultimate strength respectively). Since Eq. (19) is normalized by the material initial damage thresholds, K_0^0 , (numerically equal to the material proportional limit, σ^0), it is reasonable to assume that the resulting calibration is applicable for high strength steel grades with similar mechanical properties. Thus, the constants A and B are obtained through the linear fitting shown in Fig. 2, resulting in –0.0528 and 0.487, respectively.

When it comes to the cycle-depend phase, Han et al. [27] have found that the stress relaxation throughout this stage is small enough to be neglected in applications of fatigue strength estimation. Thus, for the sake of simplicity, it is not considered here so that Eq. (19) is independent of the number of cycles, N_c .

Finally, the relaxation factor, f_{rel} , is employed to isotropically reduce the initial residual stress, $\sigma_{res_{ini}}$, such that the relaxed residual stress renders

$$\sigma_{res} = f_{rel} \cdot \sigma_{res_{ini}} \quad (20)$$

As explained in the next section, the relaxed residual stresses obtained from Eq. (20) are employed to compute the modifying factor, K_{res} , affecting the fatigue strength of the base material.

2.4. Fatigue state function

Following the format proposed by Oller et al. [16], the fatigue state function, $f_{red}(N_c, R, \sigma_{max})$, is formulated here to take advantage of the extensive fatigue experimental data available in the literature in the form of S–N (Wöhler) curves. According to that, a fatigue strength surface for the base material is first postulated. Depending on the number of cycles, N_c , and the stress ratio, R , it reads

$$S'(R, N_c) = S'_{th}(R) + [S_u - S'_{th}(R)] \cdot \exp[-\alpha_t(R) \cdot (\log_{10} N_c)^{\beta_f}] \quad (21)$$

where

$$S'_{th}(R) = \begin{cases} S_e + (S_u - S_e) \cdot \left(\frac{1+R}{2}\right)^{S_{th,R1}}, & \text{if } |R| \leq 1 \\ S_e + (S_u - S_e) \cdot \left(\frac{1+R}{2R}\right)^{S_{th,R2}}, & \text{if } |R| > 1, \end{cases} \quad (22)$$

is the base material fatigue limit function defining the stress level above which a given material point undergoes fatigue degradation due to the application of cyclic loads, whereas $\alpha_t(R)$ is a model parameter given by

$$\alpha_t(R) = \begin{cases} \alpha_f + \left(\frac{1+R}{2}\right) \cdot \text{AUX R1}, & \text{if } |R| \leq 1 \\ \alpha_f - \left(\frac{1+R}{2R}\right) \cdot \text{AUX R2}, & \text{if } |R| > 1. \end{cases} \quad (23)$$

In Eqs. (21) and (22), S_u and S_e represent the material ultimate strength and the fatigue limit at $R = -1$, respectively. In addition, $S_{th,R1}$, $S_{th,R2}$, α_f , β_f , AUX R1 and AUX R2 in Eqs. (21)–(23) are material parameters to be calibrated from S–N experimental data.

After this, $S'_{th}(R)$ and, consequently, the S–N–R surface of Eq. (21) are modified to account for the effect of the cutting operation on the material fatigue strength, as detailed in the next section. Then, the fatigue state function, $f_{red}(N_c, R, \sigma_{max})$, is postulated as the exponential function

$$f_{red}(N_c, R, \sigma_{max}) = \exp\left[\frac{\ln(\sigma_{max}/S_u)}{(\log_{10} N_f)^{\beta_f}} \cdot (\log_{10} N_c)^{\beta_f}\right] \quad (24)$$

such that it intersects resulting S–N–R surface normalized by the material ultimate strength, i.e., $S(R, N_c)/S_u$, at the number of cycles N_f , corresponding to the normalized maximum stress, σ_{max}/S_u , as illustrated in Fig. 3 for a given stress ratio, R . Accordingly, the number of cycles N_f , in Eq. (24) can be determined by imposing σ_{max} in Eq. (21) modified to account for the cutting operation effect. Thus, it reads

$$N_f(R, \sigma_{max}) = 10^{\left\{-\frac{1}{\alpha_t(R)} \cdot \ln\left[\frac{\sigma_{max} - S_{th}(R)}{S_u - S_{th}(R)}\right] \frac{1}{\beta_f}\right\}} \quad (25)$$

where $S_{th}(R)$ is the fatigue limit function of the material affected by the shear-cutting process.

2.5. Effect of the cutting operation on the material fatigue strength

It is a common knowledge that shear-cutting operations lead to a decrease of the base material fatigue strength in the cut surface region, i.e., in the so-called shear-affected zone. This effect is incorporated in the current formulation through the modification of the base material fatigue limit function, $S'_{th}(R)$, at a given stress ratio, R . Accordingly, the resulting fatigue limit function renders

$$S_{th}(R) = K_{res} \cdot K_r \cdot S'_{th}(R), \quad (26)$$

where K_{res} is a modifying factor accounting for the effect of residual stresses and K_r a reduction factor which incorporates the influence of the cut surface roughness, as detailed in the following.

Fig. 3. Normalized Wöhler curve and f_{red} as function of the number of cycles, N_c , for a given stress ratio R and maximum stress σ_{max} . Source: Adapted from [35].

2.5.1. Residual stress factor K_{res}

As mentioned earlier, residual stresses produce a mean stress effect on the material nominal fatigue strength. In addition, experimental evidences suggest that the fatigue strength is particularly affected by the residual stresses in the loading direction [14,27]. However, the stresses arising from shear-cutting operations are usually characterized by complex triaxial states. To accommodate this directional effect, the residual stresses at the critical plane for fracture are used here to compute the modifying factor, K_{res} . Oriented according to the normal unit vector, \mathbf{n}_{crit} , this plane is defined in this work as the one at which the stress norm resulting from the applied load is a maximum. Thus, for von Mises, \mathbf{n}_{crit} is given such that the normal stress component

$$\sigma_n = \mathbf{n}_{crit}^T \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}_0 \cdot \mathbf{n}_{crit} \tag{27}$$

and the shear one

$$\tau = \|\boldsymbol{\sigma}_0 \cdot \mathbf{n}_{crit} - \sigma_n \mathbf{n}_{crit}\| \tag{28}$$

maximize the corresponding in-plane stress norm

$$f(\boldsymbol{\sigma}_0)|_{n_{crit}} = \sqrt{\sigma_n^2 + 3\tau^2}. \tag{29}$$

The critical plane orientation is computed in the current formulation once in every load cycle when the maximum stress, σ_{max} , is detected at each material point. Consequently, $f(\boldsymbol{\sigma}_0)|_{n_{crit}}$ in Eq. (29) corresponds to an in-plane measure of σ_{max} .

According to this, the residual stress modifying factor K_{res} is computed here following the experimental work by Shiozaki et al. [14] who accurately predicted the fatigue limit of high strength steel punched specimens employing the Goodman mean stress correction equation. Thus, it is defined as

$$K_{res} = \left\{ 1 - \left[\frac{\text{sgn}(\sigma_{res})|_{n_{crit}} \cdot f(\sigma_{res})|_{n_{crit}} + f_d \cdot \sigma_m}{S_u} \right] \right\} \cdot \left(\frac{1-R}{2} \right), \tag{30}$$

with

$$\text{sgn}(\sigma_{res})|_{n_{crit}} = \frac{\sigma_{res_n}}{\|\sigma_{res_n}\|}. \tag{31}$$

being a sign function depending on the direction of the residual stress normal component, σ_{res_n} , at the critical plane.

Following the rationale presented in Gustafsson et al. [36], the in-plane residual stress norm, $f(\sigma_{res})|_{n_{crit}}$, is superimposed on the nominal mean stress, $\sigma_m = \frac{(1+R)}{2} \sigma_{max}$, modified by the factor f_d , in Eq. (30). Introduced here to account for the directional effect on the mean stress, this factor is given by

$$f_d = \frac{f(\boldsymbol{\sigma}_0)|_{n_{crit}}}{\sigma_{max}}. \tag{32}$$

Finally, the term $\frac{(1-R)}{2}$ is included as a conversion factor to accommodate the fact that the present model is formulated in terms of maximum stresses whereas K_{res} was originally devised for stress amplitudes.

According to Eq. (30), K_{res} acts as a reduction factor assuming values between 0 and 1 for tensile total mean stresses, i.e., $\text{sgn}(\sigma_{res})|_{n_{crit}} \cdot f(\sigma_{res})|_{n_{crit}} + f_d \cdot \sigma_m > 0$. Contrarily, $K_{res} > 1$ under compressive total mean stresses, improving the material nominal fatigue limit. The use of the same expression on the compressive mean stress range is here supported by Chang et al. [37] who reported a good correlation between experiments and the Goodman equation prediction under this condition. Finally, K_{res} is assumed to be 1 in the absence of residual stresses, i.e., when $f(\sigma_{res})|_{n_{crit}} = 0$.

2.5.2. Surface roughness factor K_r

In addition to residual stresses, shear-cutting operations introduce geometrical defects, i.e., small and large notches on the cut surface that compromise the material fatigue strength at this region. This effect is implicitly taken into account here through the roughness reduction factor, K_r . This factor is usually empirically defined and multiple expressions are available in the literature. In this work, the expression introduced in the FKM-guideline [38,39] is employed for this purpose. For normal stresses, this equation renders

$$K_r = 1 - a_r \log_{10}(R_z) \log_{10} \left(\frac{2S_u}{S_{u,min}} \right), \tag{33}$$

where R_z represents the mean peak to valley height of the roughness profile in μm whereas a_r and $S_{u,min}$ are material parameters. For steels, their typical values are 0.22 and 400 MPa, respectively. R_z values, in turn, are obtained from roughness measurements of the specimen cut surfaces. As detailed in Section 3, it is important to distinguish the measurements of the different cutting zones due to the variation in the roughness between them.

The simplification of using the K_r factor for reduction of the fatigue strength due to surface roughness effects is very convenient as compared to modeling the actual surface geometry on micro-scale to geometrically resolve the roughness contribution. This would require detailed surface measurements which then have to be translated to a mesh of extremely fine size. Reducing the element size down to micrometers would increase the number of elements drastically, leading to a significant impact on the simulation time.

2.6. Notch effect on the maximum stress

According to the local yielding theory, plasticity-induced stress redistribution at a notch root caused by cyclic loading leads to an actual local maximum stress, σ_{max} , that is lower than σ'_{max} calculated through the product between the average stress, σ_{avg} , and the elastic stress concentration factor, K_t , [38]. It is

$$\sigma_{max} < \sigma'_{max} = K_t \cdot \sigma_{avg}, \quad (34)$$

with σ_{avg} being obtained as the ratio of the applied force to the cross-sectional area. In line with this, Lanning et al. [40] report a slight increase in the fatigue limit of a titanium alloy when cycling notch specimens with high stresses prior to conducting the rest of the test at lower levels in the high cycle regime. This suggests that the stress redistribution induced in the first stage of the experiment led to an actual local maximum stress in the second one that is lower than that of a reference case carried out without the high-stress phase.

Depending on the applied load and the severity of the stress concentration, this effect is more noticeable towards the low cycle regime, where the stresses are typically high. Considering this, the actual maximum stress is estimated in this work by

$$\sigma_{max} = \left(\frac{1}{K_t} \right)^{(1-h_i)} \sigma'_{max}, \quad (35)$$

with

$$h_i = \frac{1}{6} \log_{10} (N_c), \quad (36)$$

being the logarithmic function proposed by Gustafsson et al. [36]. It varies from 0 at the first cycle up to 1 beyond $N_c = 10^6$ and is employed here to gradually increase the actual maximum stress from the low cycle domain where fatigue is predominantly governed by plasticity-induced mechanisms to the high cycle one in which it is damage-dominated. In addition, since the applied load and the corresponding stress field are known, the stress concentration factor, K_t , is computed through Eq. (34) at the material point level in the first load cycle. Fig. 4 illustrates how σ_{max} varies from σ_{avg} at the first cycle up to σ'_{max} from $N_c = 10^6$, considering a K_t equal to 2.24 which is the theoretical value calculated for the punched specimens simulated in the present work [36]. The implications of the notch effect on applications of fatigue life estimation are further discussed in the Section 5.

2.7. Advance in time strategy

The constitutive formulation presented in this section is conceptually conceived to represent the material progressive degradation resulting from the application of cyclic loads in a cycle-by-cycle manner. However, in practical terms – when implemented in a numerical framework, e.g., based on the finite element method, – the execution of cycle-by-cycle simulations is often computationally highly-intensive, particularly for cases in the high cycle domain. For this reason, the advance in time strategy (AITS) algorithm presented by Oller et al. [16] and further developed by Barbu et al. [17] is coupled with the present model to enable the simulation of HCF cases at affordable computational costs. This algorithm consists of a load-tracking phase followed by a large increments one. Accordingly, the formalism devised in this section at the material point level is translated into Gauss point (GP) calculations in a finite element framework, as shown in the following.

Fig. 4. Actual maximum stress, σ_{max} , normalized by the calculated one, σ'_{max} , as a function of the number of cycles, N_c , for a stress concentration factor, $K_t = 2.24$.

2.7.1. Load-tracking phase

In this phase, each cycle is divided into a user-defined number of load increments and the corresponding stress norm is tracked in each GP of the finite element mesh. Accordingly, the actual maximum, σ_{max} , and minimum, σ_{min} , stresses are detected and the respective stress ratio, R , computed. After this, the current R value is compared with the previous one and if it converges at all the GPs, then a stable load condition is reached. This holds when the inequality

$$\eta = \sum_{GP} \left\| \frac{R_{GP}^{j+1} - R_{GP}^j}{R_{GP}^{j+1}} \right\| \leq tol, \quad (37)$$

is fulfilled, where tol is a user-defined convergence tolerance and $R_{GP}^j = \frac{\sigma_{min}}{\sigma_{max}} \Big|_{GP}^j$ the “ j -th” stress ratio computed at the “GP- th ” Gauss point. Once this condition is reached, the large increment phase is activated.

2.7.2. Large increments phase

The fulfillment of inequality (37) ensures that both maximum stress, σ_{max} , and stress ratio R are stable at all the GP of the finite element model. As a result, the number of cycles, N_c , becomes the only independent variable defining the fatigue state function and also the actual maximum stress in this phase, i.e., $f_{red}(N_c)$ and $\sigma_{max}(N_c)$. Benefiting from this, an advance in the simulation time may be applied, computing their evolution according to the corresponding jump in the number of cycles, while the stress ratio, R is kept constant. After this, the condition of stability is checked and if the model remains stable, a new jump may be carried out, otherwise the load-tracking phase is again activated. As it tracks the convergence of the stress ratio, R , to ensure the model stability, the AITS algorithm is able to naturally identify changes in loads and boundaries conditions applying the cycle-jump accordingly. In addition, two different types of cycle-jumps may be applied depending on the model state. Prior to damage initiation, one single jump takes the model to the cycle, N_d , defined by the mesh GP at which damage first starts. After this point, user-defined cycle-jumps, N_c^{user} , are applied whenever the condition of stability is reached. As derived in Gonçalves Junior et al. [18], the initial jump is obtained through the following expression

$$N_d(R, \sigma_{max}) \Big|_{GP} = N_f \left[\frac{\ln(\sigma_{max}/\sigma^0)}{\ln(\sigma_{max}/S_u)} \right], \quad (38)$$

with N_d being the minimum value computed across all of the mesh GPs, i.e., $\min \{ N_d \Big|_{GP} \}$. Since Eq. (38) depends on the actual maximum

Fig. 5. Schematic representation of (a) shear cutting process setup and (b) cut edge zones. From [42], used under Creative Commons CC-BY license.

stress which is, in turn, a function of the number of cycles, the N_d jump has to be iteratively calculated.

3. Phenomenology of shear-cutting operations

Shear-cutting operations such as trimming and punching typically result in a cut edge morphology that can be divided into four zones as illustrated in Fig. 5 [41,42]. The surface roughness of the rollover zone can generally be assumed as the same as the base material as this surface is not formed during the cutting process. This zone is also characterized by moderate tensile residual stresses in the tangential direction [14]. The characteristics of the burnish and the fracture zones differs from each other with the burnish zone often featuring a lower surface roughness and compressive tangential residual stresses, while the fracture zone exhibits a relatively rough surface and high tensile residual stresses in the tangential direction [14,43]. In terms of fatigue it is important to choose an appropriate cutting clearance [44,45], defined as the ratio of the distance between the punch and the die to the sheet thickness (see Fig. 5). Choosing this makes it possible to avoid significant burr formation, as evident in [42,46]. The punch tool radius can also affect the cut edge characteristics [9].

3.1. Modeling approach

The punching process simulation setup is described in detail in [42]. Since the same materials were studied in this work, the material models could be re-used and no further calibration was needed for the purpose of process simulations. A plane strain condition was assumed for the trimming simulations, and an axisymmetric condition for the punching cases, an approach confirmed in [46–48]. Hence, the out-of-plane shear stress components were neglected. Remeshing was utilized during the punching simulation to handle the locally extreme mesh distortions. The element edge length after remeshing was 0.02 mm size, creating a mesh density of more than 170 elements over the sheet thickness.

A methodology was developed for transferring the residual stress results from the process simulation to the fatigue models that were built with a different mesh density of six elements over the thickness. This was done by extracting the stress components of the elements along six lines, as shown in Fig. 6. The location of these lines corresponds to the centroid of each element through the thickness direction in the fatigue simulation.

3.2. Inclusion of the cutting operation effects in the fatigue modeling

Following the main characteristics featured by shear-cutting operations, residual stresses and the roughness of the cut surfaces are incorporated in this work in the fatigue modeling as the factors affecting the fatigue life of trimmed and punched specimens. In addition, the mechanical properties of the base material are accordingly updated to account for the work hardening induced by these operations and the volumetric fracture energy dissipated as a result.

Fig. 6. Example of the elements used for residual stress evaluation. From punching simulation of CP980 using cutting clearance 17% cutting clearance.

Employed to compute the relaxation factor, f_{rel} , of Eq. (19) and the modifying factor of the fatigue limit function, K_{res} , defined by Eq. (30), the residual stress profiles shown in Figs. A.1–A.6 of the Appendix are included in the fatigue model as constant values element-wise. For this purpose, these profiles are evaluated in the radial direction at the element centroids for each stress component. Accordingly, an element discretization scheme with a radial growth ratio is set to adequately capture the higher stress gradients close to the cut surface. In line with the models for the trimming and punching process simulations, the elements in this region are in the order of a few micrometers thick. Furthermore, the present models are divided into six element rows in the cutting direction to accommodate the corresponding residual stress profile, as shown in Fig. 7.

Once assigned to each element, the residual stresses are also used to update the damage initial threshold, \mathcal{K}_0^0 , at the region where the shear-cutting process induced a material hardening. Thus, \mathcal{K}_0^0 reads

$$\mathcal{K}_0^0|_{t+\Delta t} = \max \left\{ \mathcal{K}_0^0|_t, f(\sigma_{res_{ini}})|_{t+\Delta t} \right\}; \quad t = 0, \quad (39)$$

where $f(\sigma_{res_{ini}})$ is the stress norm of the initial residual stress, i.e., before the relaxation. In addition, the portion of the volumetric fracture energy dissipated by the material in the work-hardening process is subtracted from the total amount available before the cutting operation. For the hardening-exponential softening curve for damage proposed by Gonçalves Junior et al. [21], the remaining volumetric fracture energy is expressed as follows

$$g_f = (1 - \kappa_p^j) \cdot g_f^0, \quad (40)$$

where g_f^0 refers to the total volumetric fracture energy of the base material and κ_p^j , such that $\kappa_p^{i-1} \leq \kappa_p^j \leq \kappa_p^i \leq \kappa_p^n$, is the normalized plastic energy dissipation. As devised by Jiménez [49], it reads

$$\kappa_p^j = \kappa_p^{i-1} + \frac{f(\sigma_{res_{ini}})^2 - (\mathcal{K}^{i-1})^2}{2g_f^0} \cdot \left(\frac{\epsilon^i - \epsilon^{i-1}}{\mathcal{K}^i - \mathcal{K}^{i-1}} - \frac{\epsilon^0}{\sigma^0} \right), \quad (41)$$

Fig. 7. Discretization scheme employed in the fatigue finite element model: (a) trimmed and (b) punched specimens.

Fig. 8. Schematic representation of the initial numerical stress–strain for damage and its updated version accounting for the volumetric fracture energy dissipated in the punching process.

with $\kappa_p^i = 0$ for $i = 0$ and

$$\kappa_p^i = \kappa_p^{i-1} + \frac{1}{2g_f^0} \cdot \left\{ (\mathcal{K}^i + \mathcal{K}^{i-1}) \cdot (\varepsilon^i - \varepsilon^{i-1}) - [(\mathcal{K}^i)^2 - (\mathcal{K}^{i-1})^2] \cdot \left(\frac{\varepsilon^0}{\sigma^0}\right) \right\} \text{ for } i = 1 : n. \quad (42)$$

In Eqs. (41) and (42), ε^i and \mathcal{K}^i represent the uniaxial strain and damage threshold in the real space at the reference point i whereas ε^0 is the uniaxial strain corresponding to the uniaxial stress at the material proportional limit, σ^0 . Fig. 8 schematically illustrates the updated initial damage threshold and the remaining volumetric fracture energy at the material points in which hardening is induced by the cutting operation.

Finally, to account for the effect of cutting-related geometrical defects on the material fatigue strength at the cut surface, Eq. (33) has to be fed with the value of mean peak to valley height of roughness, R_z . In this work, the experimental measurements reported by Gustafsson et al. [36] are used for this purpose. Only the R_z values corresponding to the burnish and fracture zones are provided. Since the fracture zone is usually the one triggering the fatigue crack, it is a reasonable simplification to neglect the rollover and burr regions. These values are listed in Table 1 for trimmed and punched specimens and both high strength steels investigated in the present work, the HR CP800SF and HR CP980SF. As can be seen in Table 1, the surface roughness for the HR CP980SF trimmed specimens are not available. Following Gustafsson et al. [36], they are assumed to be equal to their punched counterpart.

To include the effect of the surface roughness in the fatigue model, the thickness of the first layer of elements around the hole is set to

Table 1

Mean peak to valley height of roughness profile R_z measured in the burnish (Burn.) and fracture (Frac.) zones of the punched (P) and trimmed (T) specimens with cutting clearances denoted as CCL [36].

Material	CCL	R_z Burn. [μm]	R_z Frac. [μm]
HR CP800SF (P)	8.8	4.1	21.3
HR CP800SF (T)	8.8	7.9	19.1
HR CP980SF (P)	8.6	6.5	10.1
HR CP980SF (P)	17	6.0	6.2

Fig. 9. Uniform gauge specimen for the monotonic tensile testing. The dimensions are expressed in mm and the thicknesses are 3.4 mm and 3.5 mm for the HR CP800SF and HR CP980SF, respectively.

match the R_z value of the burnish zone. Analogously, the second layer is defined so that the sum with the first equates the fracture zone R_z , as shown in the detail of Fig. 7. Owing to the small difference between the R_z values in the HR CP980SF cases with cutting clearance of 17%, both regions were modeled with only one layer of 6.2 μm . In addition, in line with the order of magnitude for the length of each zone presented in [42], the first and the first two rows of elements are defined as the burnish zone for the trimmed and punched specimens, respectively,

Fig. 10. Comparison between numerical and experimental uniaxial stress–strain curves for damage: (a) HR CP800SF and (b) HR CP980SF.

whereas the remaining five and four are assigned to the fracture one, as illustrated by the magenta and cyan colors in Fig. 7.

4. Calibration of the fatigue model

The remaining material parameters required by the constitutive model presented in Section 2 are obtained from experimental data of monotonic and fatigue tests conducted on coupon specimens. According to that, the general procedure presented in Gonçalves Junior et al. [18] is employed here to calibrate the parameters of both the HR CP800SF and HR CP980SF steels, as briefly described in the following.

4.1. Monotonic tensile test

The results from standard uniaxial tensile tests [50] were employed to calibrate the hardening-softening stress–strain curve for damage of Fig. 1. The tests were carried out on the uniform gauge specimen schematically illustrated in Fig. 9.

The conducted tests led to elastic limits, σ^0 , equal to 778 MPa and 957 MPa for the HR CP800SF and HR CP980SF, respectively. In addition, a curve fitting procedure was employed to calibrate the inelastic response of the materials at the Region II of Fig. 1 curve. To this aim, 6th-order polynomials were fitted to the corresponding region of the experimental curves. Then, the polynomials were used to generate equally spaced stress–strain pairs over this region. To complete the set of general mechanical properties required by the model, $E = 201$ MPa and $\nu = 0.263$ were adopted as Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio for both materials.

The performed calibrations were then numerically verified against the material monotonic response obtained in the experiment. For this purpose, the constitutive law presented in Section 2 was implemented in the open-source multi-disciplinary code Kratos-Multiphysics [51–53]. The pre- and post-processor GiD [54] was used to prepare the numerical model and visualize the simulation results. Taking advantage of symmetry, only one-eighth of the test specimens was modeled. The geometries were discretized with 15192 and 11403 first-order hexahedral elements for the HR CP800SF and HR CP980SF cases, respectively. A monotonically increasing load was applied as a prescribed displacement at the specimen free end. Appropriate boundary conditions were defined at the symmetry faces.

Fig. 10 shows the numerical and experimental monotonic response of both materials. The good correlation between the corresponding curves ensures a proper calibration of the material model for the monotonic loading condition in the two cases.

4.2. Fatigue test

As discussed in the author's previous work [18], the definition of the fatigue strength surface of Eq. (21) in the range of interest of this

Fig. 11. Hourglass specimens for the uniaxial fatigue testing. Dimensions without and with parentheses representing the geometries with $K_t = 1.056$ for the experiments at $R = -1$ with both materials and $K_t = 1.032$ for the HR CP800SF tests at $R = 0.1$. All of them are expressed in mm and the thicknesses are 3.4 mm and 3.5 mm for the HR CP800SF and HR CP980SF, respectively.

work, i.e., $|R| \leq 1$, relies on the calibration of four fatigue material parameters, namely: $S_{th,R1}$, α_f , β_f and AUX R1. This calibration is carried out using S–N experimental points, ideally coming from two different stress ratios. S–N pairs obtained from [42] for $R = -1$ and test data for $R = 0.1$ were employed to calibrate the HR CP800SF parameters. For the HR CP980SF, however, S–N experimental point for only $R = -1$ were available. To accommodate this restriction in the availability of experimental data, the Geber equation

$$\sigma_{max}|_{(R=0.1)} = \frac{-0.5|R-1| \cdot S_u^2 + \sqrt{0.25(R-1)^2 \cdot S_u^4 + (R+1)^2 \cdot S_u^2 \cdot \sigma_{max}^2}|_{(R=1)}}{0.5(R+1)^2 \cdot \sigma_{max}|_{(R=1)}} \quad (43)$$

was employed to generate the S–N points for $R = 0.1$ from the existing ones at $R = -1$, as it produces a good correlation with experiments for a wide variety of high strength steels [55]. To this aim, $R = 0.1$ was assigned to Eq. (43) for each maximum experimental stress, σ_{max} , at $R = -1$ with exception to the ones corresponding to the runout pairs that were not considered in this procedure.

After that, the calibration was carried out following the same approach adopted by Gonçalves Junior et al. [18]. Thus, the S–N pairs were converted into the respective ones defined at the material point level. For $R = -1$, a stress concentration factor $K_t = 1.056$ was employed for both materials, whereas $K_t = 1.032$ was used for the HR CP800SF $R = 0.1$ points. The corresponding test specimen geometries are schematically illustrated in Fig. 11 with dimensions without and with parenthesis, respectively. Following this, the converted points above the elastic limit, σ^0 , were discarded from the calibration while the runout pairs at $R = -1$ were included for both cases. The material fatigue limits, S_e , equal to 385 MPa and 398 MPa were also modified by $K_t = 1.056$ resulting in 407 and 420 MPa for the HR CP800SF and HR

Fig. 12. S–N–R surfaces resulting from the material parameters α_f , β_f , $S_{th,R1}$ and AUX R1 calibration: (a) HR CP800SF and (b) HR CP980SF. Parametric adjustment performed with converted S–N pairs of stress ratios $R = -1$ and $R = 0.1$. Runout points at 2×10^6 cycles are illustrated with arrows.

Table 2

HR CP800SF and HR CP980SF properties used in the numerical models. Young’s modulus (E), Poisson’s ratio (ν), uniaxial stress at the proportional limit (σ^0), ultimate strength, (S_u), fatigue limit (S_e), S–N–R surface fitting parameters (α_f , β_f , $S_{th,R1}$, AUX R1).

Material	General mechanical properties				Fatigue parameters				
	E (GPa)	ν (-)	σ^0 (MPa)	S_u (MPa)	S_e (MPa)	α_f (-)	β_f (-)	$S_{th,R1}$ (-)	AUX R1 (-)
HR CP800SF	201	0.263	778	835	385	0.0001667	5.736	1.691	-0.0002519
HR CP980SF			957	1034	398	0.004722	3.720	1.816	-0.006171

Fig. 13. Flowchart of the procedure to obtain the fatigue model input data.

CP980SF, respectively. In addition, tensile ultimate strengths, S_u , equal to 835 MPa and 1034 MPa obtained from the uniaxial tensile tests were used in the calibration procedure. Finally, the parametric adjustments were carried out using a Matlab [56] code based on built-in fitting functions. Fig. 12 shows the resulting S–N–R surface together with S–N material points used in the calibration and the respective calibrated parameters.

The mechanical properties and model parameters resulting from the calibration procedure presented in this section are summarized in Table 2 for both materials investigated in this work. In addition, the flowchart of Fig. 13 summarizes the procedure to obtain the fatigue model input data.

5. Results and discussion

The predictive capability of the constitutive formulation previously presented is addressed here through the numerical reproduction of the uniaxial fatigue tests on trimmed and punched specimens reported by Gustafsson et al. [36]. As mentioned earlier, two AHSS were simulated, namely: HR CP800SF and HR CP9800SF steels. Finite element models with the general arrangements shown in Fig. 14 were set for the trim-

Fig. 14. Uniaxial fatigue test specimens with cut edges highlighted in red and the respective finite element model for the cases: (a) trimming and (b) punching. Dimensions are expressed in mm.

Fig. 15. Fatigue life prediction for the HR CP800SF: (a) trimmed specimens, $R = -1$, (b) trimmed specimens, $R = 0.1$ and (c) punched specimens, $R = 0.1$. Black filled marks and lines represent the numerical S–N estimations, whereas the solid and hollow red marks depict the failure (fail.) and runout (RO) experimental points extracted from [36].

Fig. 16. Fatigue life prediction for the HR CP980SF: (a) trimmed specimens, $R = -1$, (b) trimmed specimens, $R = 0.1$ and (c) punched specimens, $R = 0.1$. Black filled marks and lines represent the numerical S–N estimations, whereas the solid and hollow red marks depict the failure (fail.) and runout (RO) experimental points extracted from [36].

ming and punching cases. Benefiting from symmetry, only one-quarter of the test specimens were modeled. Appropriate boundary conditions were set at the symmetry planes. For each case, the loads were applied as a sinusoidal prescribed displacement of constant amplitude at the specimen free end. The corresponding maximum and minimum stresses were computed through the ratio between the reaction force at the symmetry plane 1 and the respective nominal cross-section area. The specimen geometries were discretized following the scheme presented in Section 3.2. Around 16 000 and 9500 first-order hexahedral elements were employed in the trimming and punching models, respectively. Finally, the material properties listed in Table 2 were adopted according to the simulated material.

5.1. Shear cutting simulation validity

The shear cutting simulation methodology was validated in [42] using the materials studied in this work. The simulated and measured cut edge morphologies were compared. The hardness in the shear-affected zone was measured and qualitatively compared with the simulated plastic strains. Estimations for the shear-affected zone width fall within the range of 0.4–1 mm, which is in line with the microhardness measurements presented in [47,57]. The simulated and measured punch force–displacement curves were compared and, to some extent, the residual stress measurements were also compared to the simulation results. The residual stress field estimations obtained by punching process simulations are further strengthened by the fact that the corresponding residual stresses have been used with satisfactory results for fatigue life estimations in [36,43]. However, more precise validation of the stress field would be valuable but remains a challenge due to the geometry of the specimen, the small volume containing the

high stresses, and the expectedly large variations through the thickness. In a qualitative sense, the results show reasonable agreement with the observations presented in [14]. A sensitivity analysis in which the initial residual stress field is varied could also provide further insight into the fatigue lives estimated by the present model.

The surface roughness measurements are included in Table 1. These measurements were used directly in the fatigue model and were not compared to simulations of the cutting process because these simulations are not capable of predicting micro-features such as surface roughness.

5.2. Fatigue life estimation

The fatigue lives estimated by the numerical model for each case are presented as a function of stress amplitudes in the conventional S–N curve format. Accordingly, baseline simulations considering solely the residual stresses and superposed ones combining both residual stresses and surface roughness are carried out to assess the effect of these factors on the fatigue strength of each investigated material.

Figs. 15 and 16 show only a marginal difference between the baseline and superposed numerical estimations which evidences the residual stresses as the main factor affecting the fatigue life of both materials studied in this work. This prediction is in line with the experimental study conducted by Peatzold et al. [9] which reports that no correlation was found between the surface roughness at the fracture zone of the shear cut surface and the loss of fatigue strength of the dual phase steel DP800. Despite that, the suppression of the surface roughness effect may have an influence on the crack initiation location, as shown in the damage contour plot of Fig. 17. Furthermore, it also

Fig. 17. Damage contour at the onset and total failure moments of the HR CP800SF punching case considering: (a) only the residual stresses and (b) the residual stress and the surface roughness. Nominal stress amplitude, $\sigma_a = 90.4$ MPa, and stress ratio, $R = 0.1$.

Fig. 18. Accuracy of the model in estimating the fatigue lives of the trimmed (T) and punched (P) specimens at $R = -1$ and $R = 0.1$ made of (a) HR CP800SF using 8.8% cutting clearance and (b) HR CP980SF using 8.6% and 17% cutting clearances. Experimental points extracted from [36].

illustrates that the crack initiates and reaches its full length a little earlier in the simulation accounting for the surface roughness.

When it comes to the cutting clearance influence, the model estimates a conservative life for the trimmed specimens with 8.6% whereas it is more accurate for the 17% ones, see Fig. 16(a). In the punching case, in turn, the model predicts a slightly shorter life for the specimens with 17% than the ones with 8.6% while this effect is more pronounced in the experiments as shown in Fig. 16(c). As pointed out by Gustafsson et al. [36], while hole diameters produced through punching are similar at the top of the metal sheet, they increase with the cutting clearance at the bottom. Thus, the specimens with 17% cutting clearance might

be submitted to higher stresses during the test due to the smaller cross-sectional area. However, the nominal area was considered in this work, which could be one source of the discrepancy between the experimental measurements and the numerical predictions for these cases. Although potentially significant for coupon specimens, this effect should be negligible at the component level.

Fig. 18 shows the accuracy of the proposed model in estimating the fatigue lives of trimmed and punched specimens. Among the 67 experimental results reported by Gustafsson et al. [36] for the materials investigated in this work, only two corresponding to the HR CP800SF trimming case at a nominal amplitude, $\sigma_a = 216$ MPa and $R = -1$

Fig. 19. Comparison between the HR CP980SF fatigue surfaces and respective model predictions: (a) trimmed specimen, cutting clearance 8.6%, 249 MPa at $R = -1$, (b) trimmed specimen, cutting clearance 8.6%, 410 MPa at $R = -1$, (c) trimmed specimen, cutting clearance 17%, 240 MPa at $R = -1$, (d) trimmed specimen, cutting clearance 8.6%, 306 MPa at $R = 0.1$, (e) trimmed specimen, cutting clearance 8.6%, 194 MPa at $R = 0.1$ and (f) punched specimen, cutting clearance 17%, 109 MPa at $R = 0.1$. Fracture surfaces adapted from [36], used under Creative Commons CC-BY license.

could not be predicted by the present model, possibly due to the low stress level close to the runout range. All other estimations lie within the error band of factor three. Besides the HR CP980SF 8.6% trimming and 17% punching cases previously discussed, the model also provided conservative life estimations for the HR CP800SF trimmed specimens at $R = 0.1$, whereas a general trend laying around the 50% failure probability line (solid black one) is noticed for the remaining predictions.

5.3. Crack onset location and propagation pattern

The fracture surfaces of some HR CP980SF specimens are available in [36]. The comparison between the actual crack initiation points and the respective numerical counterparts is shown in Fig. 19. As experimentally observed, the model predicts the crack onset location at the fracture zone for most of the specimens. Accordingly, the cases pointed with an orange arrow in Fig. 19(a), (e) and (f) exhibit remarkable numerical–experimental correlations.

Both the experimentally determined and numerically predicted regions for crack initiation are consistent with the shear cutting simulations in [42], where large tensile residual stresses occur in the fracture zone together with a rougher surface than in the burnish zone. Furthermore, there is a large variability in the exact location of the initiation site within the fracture zone, as discussed in [36]. On the other hand, the predictions of the numerical model are constrained by the finite element mesh resolution so that the comparative results shown in Fig. 19 should be taken only as a general guideline for the crack initiation points, not as a definitive answer.

Despite the general trend, the trimming case with 17% cutting clearance, submitted to $\sigma_a = 240$ MPa at $R = -1$ arises as an exception in which damage initiates at the sub-surface adjacent to the fracture zone (see the detail of Fig. 19(c)). This behavior can possibly be attributed to the fact that the applied load is not high enough to relax the residual stress peak at the nucleation region close to the cut surface (see Fig. A.5(d)) while the roughness measured at the fracture zone of the 17% specimens produces a more discrete influence on the material fatigue strength than in the other cases, as evidenced by the R_z values of Table 1.

Fig. 20 describes how the relaxation factor, f_{rel} , fatigue state function, $f_{red}(\gamma)$, and damage, d , evolve from the intact specimen condition up to its complete failure in the cases simulated here. The punching

case of Fig. 19(f) is used as a reference for this analysis. First, the stress generated by the applied load induces the residual stress relaxation in the GPs in which the condition of Eq. (19) is fulfilled. This first-stage monotonic-like relaxation occurs mainly during the first cycle and is concentrated in the region close to the cut surface where the residual stresses are higher, as shown in Fig. 20(a). Here, it is noteworthy to mention that the resulting relaxed residual stresses are solely employed in this work to modify the material fatigue strength through the factor K_{res} defined in Eq. (30). Owing to this, the initial relaxation process does not perturb the model stress field so that it remains stable right from the first cycle. With the use of the AITS algorithm, the stability condition of inequality (37) is fulfilled after the third cycle and the N_d cycle-jump of Eq. (38) is performed according to the mesh GP at which damage first start (see Fig. 20(j)). In addition, the fatigue state function also evolves thoroughly magnifying the stress norm, $f(\sigma_0)$, in the blue region shown in Fig. 20(f). However, since this evolution combined with the stress redistribution triggered by the damage onset are not high enough to cause the immediate crack propagation, the model reaches a new stable condition. Accordingly, user-defined cycle-jumps, N_c^{user} , of less than 10% of the specimen total life estimation are applied to efficiently handle the phase right after the damage onset. After this stage, $f_{red}(\gamma)$ undergoes a rapid evolution (Fig. 20(g) and (h)) driving the damage propagation throughout the specimen cross-section in just few cycles – 40 cycles in this case –, as shown in Fig. 20(k) and (l). This final phase is then accompanied by a rapid residual stress relaxation (Fig. 20(d)) due to the crack extension effect [23]. As discussed in Section 2.3, the relaxation model proposed in this work is cycle-independent so that no significant f_{rel} evolution is noted in-between of the initial and final simulation stages (see Fig. 20(b) and (c)).

5.4. Notch effect on the fatigue life estimation

Finally, Fig. 21 compares the fatigue life estimations as a function of stress amplitude for the cases that consider the notch effect on the maximum stress, as discussed in Section 2.6, with those in which it is neglected. Apart from numerical deviations, the estimations concerning the trimmed specimen are almost coincident as a result of a nearly uniform stress distribution across the cross-section (see Fig. 21(a) and (b)). However, as the notch radius decreases the discrepancy between the curves increase due to the higher stress concentration severity, as

Fig. 20. Evolution of the (a)–(d) residual stress relation factor, (e)–(h) fatigue state function and (i)–(l) damage for the HR CP980SF punching cases with 17% cutting clearance submitted to a nominal stress amplitude $\sigma_a = 109$ MPa at $R = 0.1$.

Fig. 21. Comparison between the fatigue life prediction considering the notch effect on the maximum stress and the case in which no correction is applied for the HR CP800SF: (a) trimmed specimens, $R = -1$, (b) trimmed specimens, $R = 0.1$ and (c) punched specimens, $R = 0.1$.

shown in Fig. 21(c) for the HR CP800SF punched specimen investigated in this work. In this case, neglecting the notch effect on the maximum stress results in conservative estimations, particularly toward the low cycle regime.

6. Conclusions

In this work, a numerical model to predict the effect of shear-cutting operations on the fatigue life of high strength steels was presented. Based on an isotropic damage-based high cycle fatigue constitutive law, this formulation incorporates the effect of residual stresses and the

roughness of the cut surfaces as process-related factors affecting the fatigue strength of the base material. In addition to that, standard mechanical properties coming from uniaxial tensile tests and S–N data obtained with as-polished specimens are the only material information required to perform the model calibration.

The predictive capability of the present constitutive formulation was assessed through the numerical reproduction of the uniaxial fatigue tests on trimmed and punched specimens conducted by Gustafsson et al. [36]. Residual stress profiles coming from trimming and punching simulations and the roughness of the cut surfaces measured in actual test specimens were used as process-related data. The obtained results

show that while the residual stresses constitute the main factor affecting the model fatigue life predictions, accounting for the effect of cut surface roughness is essential to properly capture the onset location of the fatigue cracks.

In concrete terms, the model was able to estimate the fatigue life of 65 out of the 67 no-runout S–N points available in [36] for the two materials investigated in this work. All of them were below an error factor of three. Excepted for two conservative and one non-conservative S–N curve estimations, all other predictions presented a general trend laying around the 50% failure probability line. As experimentally observed, the model predicted the fracture zone as the crack initiation region for most of the simulated cases. Despite factors such as the probabilistic nature of fatigue in metals and the difficulty to localize the exact nucleation point of the actual cracks, some of the numerical cases achieved a good correlation with the experiments for the onset location.

The notch effect on the maximum stress was also discussed, showing that the present model delivers conservative fatigue life predictions toward the low cycle regime when this effect is neglected in high stress concentration cases, such as the punching ones simulated in this work.

Finally, it is noteworthy to mention that the model can not only handle coupon specimen cases, but is straightforwardly extensible to component-level applications, enabling the assessment of metallic engineering structures whose fatigue strength is affected by features obtained through shear-cutting operations.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

L.A. Gonçalves Junior: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Investigation, Formal analysis.
S. Jiménez: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Software, Project

administration, Formal analysis. **A. Cornejo:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Software, Conceptualization. **D. Gustafsson:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Software, Methodology, Investigation. **E. Olsson:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation. **L.G. Barbu:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

This work has been done within the framework of the Fatigue4Light (H2020-LC-GV-06-2020) project: “Fatigue modeling and fast testing methodologies to optimize part design and to boost lightweight materials deployment in chassis parts”. This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 101006844. It has also been supported through the FatSAM project funded by the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation program under grant agreement No 101159809. The authors Lucia Gratiela Barbu and Alejandro Cornejo are Serra Hunter Fellows. The authors gratefully acknowledge all the received support.

Appendix. Residual stress profiles obtained from the simulations of the trimming and punching processes

Fig. A.1. Distribution of the initial residual stress components in the radial direction predicted for the HR CP800SF trimmed specimens with 8.8% cutting clearance: (a) to (f) corresponding to the 1st to 6th rows of elements from top to bottom cut surfaces.

Fig. A.2. Distribution of the initial residual stress components in the radial direction predicted for the HR CP800SF punched specimens with 8.8% cutting clearance: (a) to (f) corresponding to the 1st to 6th rows of elements from top to bottom cut surfaces.

Fig. A.3. Distribution of the initial residual stress components in the radial direction predicted for the HR CP980SF trimmed specimens with 8.6% cutting clearance: (a) to (f) corresponding to the 1st to 6th rows of elements from top to bottom cut surfaces.

Fig. A.4. Distribution of the initial residual stress components in the radial direction predicted for the HR CP980SF punched specimens with 8.6% cutting clearance: (a) to (f) corresponding to the 1st to 6th rows of elements from top to bottom cut surfaces.

Fig. A.5. Distribution of the initial residual stress components in the radial direction predicted for the HR CP980SF trimmed specimens with 17% cutting clearance: (a) to (f) corresponding to the 1st to 6th rows of elements from top to bottom cut surfaces.

Fig. A.6. Distribution of the initial residual stress components in the radial direction predicted for the HR CP980SF trimmed specimens with 17% cutting clearance: (a) to (f) corresponding to the 1st to 6th rows of elements from top to bottom cut surfaces.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- [1] Goede M. Superlight-car project-an integrated research approach for lightweight car body innovations. In: *Proceedings of the international conference on innovative developments for lightweight vehicle structures*. Wolfsburg, Germany; 2009, p. 25–38.
- [2] Lara A, Frómata D, Parareda S, Casellas D, Larour P, Hinterdorfer J, Atzema E, Heuse M. Sheared edge formability characterization of cold-rolled advanced high strength steels for automotive applications. *IOP Conf Ser: Mater Sci Eng* 2022;1238(1):012029. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/1238/1/012029>.
- [3] Madivala M, Bleck W. Strain rate dependent mechanical properties of TWIP steel. *J Manuf Sci Eng* 2019;71(4):1291–302. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s11837-018-3137-0>.
- [4] Nasheralahkami S, Zhou W, Golovashchenko S. Study of sheared edge formability of ultra-high strength DP980 sheet metal blanks. *J Manuf Sci Eng* 2019;141(9). <http://dx.doi.org/10.1115/1.4044098>.
- [5] Thomas DJ. Characterization of cut-edges for improved automotive chassis and suspension fatigue CAE life predictions. *J Fail Anal Prev* 2012;12(4):408–18. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s11668-012-9577-x>.
- [6] Kleiner M, Geiger M, Klaus A. Manufacturing of lightweight components by metal forming. *CIRP Ann* 2003;52(2):521–42. [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0007-8506\(07\)60202-9](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0007-8506(07)60202-9).
- [7] Lara A, Picas I, Casellas D. Effect of the cutting process on the fatigue behaviour of press hardened and high strength dual phase steels. *J Mater Process Technol* 2013;213(11):1908–19. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jmatprotec.2013.05.003>.
- [8] Stahl J, Müller D, Pätzold I, Golle R, Tobie T, Volk W, Stahl K. The influence of residual stresses induced by near-net-shape blanking processes on the fatigue behavior under bending loads. *IOP Publ* 2019;651(1):012086. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/651/1/012086>.
- [9] Paetzold I, Dittmann F, Feistle M, Golle R, Haefele P, Hoffmann H, Volk W. Influence of shear cutting parameters on the fatigue behavior of a dual-phase steel. *IOP Publ* 2017;896(1):012107. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/896/1/012107>.
- [10] Paetzold I, Feistle M, Golle R, Volk W, Frehn A, Ilksens R. Determination of the minimum possible damage due to shear cutting using a multi-stage shear cutting process. *IOP Publ* 2018;418(1):012107. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/418/1/012107>.
- [11] Björkblad A, Skrinjar O. Influence of cut edges on fatigue properties for UHSS materials. *Tech. rep.*, 2009.
- [12] Meurling F, Melander A, Linder J, Larsson M. The influence of mechanical and laser cutting on the fatigue strengths of carbon and stainless sheet steels. *Scand J Metall* 2001;30(5):309–19. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1034/j.1600-0692.2001.300506.x>.
- [13] Standard practice for conducting force controlled constant amplitude axial fatigue tests of metallic materials. *Tech. rep.*, West Conshohocken, PA: ASTM International; 2021, URL www.astm.org.
- [14] Shiozaki T, Tamai Y, Urabe T. Effect of residual stresses on fatigue strength of high strength steel sheets with punched holes. *Int J Fatigue* 2015;80:324–31. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfatigue.2015.06.018>.
- [15] Sperle J. Fatigue strength of high strength dual-phase steel sheet. *Int J Fatigue* 1985;7(2):79–86. [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0142-1123\(85\)90037-4](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0142-1123(85)90037-4).
- [16] Oller S, Salomón O, Oñate E. A continuum mechanics model for mechanical fatigue analysis. *Comput Mater Sci* 2005;32(2):175–95. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.commatsci.2004.08.001>.
- [17] Barbu L, Oller S, Martínez X, Barbat A. High cycle fatigue simulation: A new stepwise load-advancing strategy. *Eng Struct* 2015;97:118–29. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.engstruct.2015.04.012>.
- [18] Gonçalves L, Jiménez S, Cornejo A, Tedesco M, Barbu L. A high cycle fatigue numerical framework for component-level virtual fatigue testing: Application to a light-duty vehicle lower control arm. *Eng Struct* 2024;311:118198. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.engstruct.2024.118198>.
- [19] Simo J, Ju J. Strain- and stress-based continuum damage models – I. Formulation. *Int J Solids Struct* 1987;23:821–40. [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0020-7683\(87\)90083-7](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0020-7683(87)90083-7).
- [20] Barbat G, Cervera M, Chiumenti M, Espinoza E. Structural size effect: Experimental, theoretical and accurate computational assessment. *Eng Struct* 2020;213:110555. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.engstruct.2020.110555>.
- [21] Gonçalves L, Jiménez S, Cornejo A, Barbu L, Parareda S, Casellas D. Numerical simulation of a rapid fatigue test of high Mn-TWIP steel via a high cycle fatigue constitutive law. *Int J Fatigue* 2023;168:107444. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfatigue.2022.107444>.
- [22] Zobeck P, Klemenc J. Application of a nonlinear kinematic-isotropic material model for the prediction of residual stress relaxation under a cyclic load. *Int J Fatigue* 2021;150:106290. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfatigue.2021.106290>.
- [23] Vaara J, Kunnari A, Frondelius T. Literature review of fatigue assessment methods in residual stressed state. *Eng Fail Anal* 2020;110:104379. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.engfailanal.2020.104379>.
- [24] Zaroog OS, Ali A, Sahari BB, Zahari R. Modelling of residual stress relaxation: A review. *Pertanika J Sci Technol* 2009;17.
- [25] Zaroog OS, Ali A, Sahari B, Zahari R. Modeling of residual stress relaxation of fatigue in 2024-T351 aluminum alloy. *Int J Fatigue* 2011;33:279–85. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfatigue.2010.08.012>.

- [26] Hayama M, Kikuchi S, Tsukahara M, Misaka Y, Komotori J. Estimation of residual stress relaxation in low alloy steel with different hardness during fatigue by in situ X-ray measurement. *Int J Fatigue* 2024;178:107989. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfatigue.2023.107989>.
- [27] Han S, Lee T, Shin B. Residual stress relaxation of welded steel components under cyclic load. *Steel Res* 2002;73:414–20. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/srin.200200008>.
- [28] Zhuang WZ, Halford GR. Investigation of residual stress relaxation under cyclic load. *Int J Fatigue* 2001;23:31–7. [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0142-1123\(01\)00132-3](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0142-1123(01)00132-3).
- [29] Leitner M, Khurshid M, Barsoum Z. Stability of high frequency mechanical impact (HFMI) post-treatment induced residual stress states under cyclic loading of welded steel joints. *Eng Struct* 2017;143:589–602. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.engstruct.2017.04.046>.
- [30] Kim J-C, Cheong S-K, Noguchi H. Residual stress relaxation and low- and high-cycle fatigue behavior of shot-peened medium-carbon steel. *Int J Fatigue* 2013;56:114–22. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfatigue.2013.07.001>.
- [31] Hemmesi K, Mallet P, Farajian M. Numerical evaluation of surface welding residual stress behavior under multiaxial mechanical loading and experimental validations. *Int J Mech Sci* 2020;168:105127. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijmeccsci.2019.105127>.
- [32] Morrow J, Sinclair G. Cycle-dependent stress relaxation. In: *Symposium on basic mechanisms of fatigue: presented at the sixty-first annual meeting, American society for testing materials*. Boston, Massachusetts; 1958.
- [33] Jhansale H, Topper T. Engineering analysis of the inelastic stress response of a structural metal under variable cyclic strains. In: *Cyclic stress-strain behavior—analysis, experimentation, and failure prediction*. ASTM International; 1971.
- [34] S. K. The behaviour of residual stress during fatigue stress cycles. In: *Proceedings of the international conference of mechanical behaviour of materials*. vol. 2, Kyoto: Society of Material Science; 1972, p. 111–8.
- [35] Jiménez S, Barbu L, Oller S, Cornejo A. On the numerical study of fatigue process in rail heads by means of an isotropic damage based high-cycle fatigue constitutive law. *Eng Fail Anal* 2022;131:105915. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.engfailanal.2021.105915>.
- [36] Gustafsson D, Parareda S, Munier R, Olsson E. High cycle fatigue life estimation of punched and trimmed specimens considering residual stresses and surface roughness. *Int J Fatigue* 2024;186:108384. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfatigue.2024.108384>.
- [37] Chang S, Zhang K, Tan J, Tu S. The effect of residual stress on high-cycle fatigue properties and its evaluation method of Ti-6Al-4V alloy. *Fatigue Fract Eng Mater Struct* 2024;47(10):3633–45. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/ffe.14397>.
- [38] McKelvey SA, Lee Y-L, Barkley ME. Stress-based uniaxial fatigue analysis using methods described in FKM-guideline. *J Fail Anal Prev* 2012;12(5):445–84. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s11668-012-9599-4>.
- [39] Rennert R, Vormwald M, Esderts A. FKM-guideline “analytical strength assessment” – background and current developments. *Int J Fatigue* 2024;182:108165. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfatigue.2024.108165>.
- [40] Lanning D, Haritos GK, Nicholas T, Maxwell DC. Low-cycle fatigue/high-cycle fatigue interactions in notched Ti-6Al-4V. *Fatigue Fract Eng Mater Struct* 2001;24(9):565–77. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1046/j.1460-2695.2001.00411.x>.
- [41] VDI 2906-2:1994. Quality of cut faces of (sheet) metal parts after cutting, blanking, trimming or piercing; shearing, form of sheared edge and characteristic values. Berlin: Association of German Engineers, Engl. VDI-Gesellschaft Produktion und Logistik.
- [42] Gustafsson D, Parareda S, Ortiz-Membrado L, Mateo A, Jiménez-Piqué E, Olsson E. Simulation of metal punching and trimming using minimal experimental characterization. *J Mater Process Technol* 2023;321:118148. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jmatprotec.2023.118148>.
- [43] Gustafsson D, Parareda S, Sieurin H, Olsson E. Estimating the effect of punching on out-of-plane bending fatigue of steel sheet specimens. *Eng Fail Anal* 2025;173:109415. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/J.ENGFAILANAL.2025.109415>.
- [44] Maronne E, Galtier A, Robert J-L, Ishikawa T. Cutting process influence on fatigue steel sheets properties. *WIT Trans Eng Sci* 2003;40:508. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2495/FDM030021>.
- [45] Maronne E, Labesse-Jied F, Galtier A, Robert JL. Influence of a cut edge on steel sheets fatigue properties. *Fatigue* 2003;2:18–24.
- [46] Sandin O, Rodríguez JM, Larour P, Parareda S, Frómeta D, Hammarberg S, Kajberg J, Casellas D. A particle finite element method approach to model shear cutting of high-strength steel sheets. *Comput Part Mech* 2024;11:1863–86. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/S40571-023-00708-5>.
- [47] Pätzold I, Stahl J, Golle R, Volk W. Reducing the shear affected zone to improve the edge formability using a two-stage shear cutting simulation. *J Mater Process Technol* 2023;313:117872. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/J.JMATPROTEC.2023.117872>.
- [48] Sandin O, Larour P, Rodríguez JM, Parareda S, Hammarberg S, Kajberg J, Casellas D. Numerical modelling of shear cutting in complex phase high strength steel sheets: A comprehensive study using the particle finite element method. *Finite Elem Anal Des* 2025;246:104331. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/J.FINEL.2025.104331>.
- [49] Jiménez S, Barbu L, Cornejo A, Oller S. Plastic-damage model for cyclic loading. Use of the rule of mixtures in homogeneous materials. *Comput Methods Appl Mech Engrg* 2025;442:118033. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.cma.2025.118033>.
- [50] Metallic materials – Tensile testing. Part 1: Method of test at room temperature. Tech. rep., Vernier, Geneva: International Organization for Standardization; 2016, URL www.iso.org.
- [51] Dadvand P, Rossi R, Oñate E. An object-oriented environment for developing finite element codes for multi-disciplinary applications. *Arch Comput Methods Eng* 2010;17:253–97. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s11831-010-9045-2>.
- [52] Dadvand P, Rossi R, Gil M, Martorell X, Cotela J, Juanpere E, Idelsohn S, Oñate E. Migration of a generic multi-physics framework to HPC environments. *Comput & Fluid* 2013;80:301–9. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.compfluid.2012.02.004>.
- [53] Ferrándiz VM, Bucher P, Zorrilla R, Rossi R, Jcotela, Velázquez AC, Celigueta MA, Maria J, tteschemacher, Roig C, miguelmaso, Casas G, Warnakulasuriya S, Núñez M, Dadvand P, Latorre S, de Pouplana I, González JI, Arrufat F, riccardotosi, Ghantasala A, Wilson P, AFranci, dbaumgaertner, Chandra B, Geiser A, Sautter KB, Lopez I, lluis, Gárate J. KratosMultiphysics/Kratos: release 9.2. 2022. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7084882>.
- [54] Ribó R, Pasenau M, Escolano E, Ronda J, Coll A. GiD user manual. CIMNE; 2007.
- [55] Luo Y, Zhang B, Song Z, Luo X, Zhang G. The high-throughput bridge to the rapid evaluation of fatigue reliability of structural engineering materials. *Int J Fatigue* 2024;178:107966. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfatigue.2023.107966>.
- [56] MATLAB. version 9.7.0 (R2019b). Natick, Massachusetts: The MathWorks Inc.; 2019.
- [57] Stahl J, Pätzold I, Golle R, Sunderkötter C, Sieurin H, Volk W. Effect of one- and two-stage shear cutting on the fatigue strength of truck frame parts. *J Manuf Mater Process* 2020;4(2):52. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/jmmp4020052>.